

Towards AI-Enabled Engineering of Digital Twins: An Architecture-Centric Approach

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Abstract—Digital twins (DTs) are virtual replica of a physical/digital system that mirror the state and behaviour of physical entities via continuous synchronisation or predictive simulation. The engineering of DT not only involves several effort-intensive and complex tasks such as selecting physical aspects to be replicated, onboarding data streams, and developing a DT model. Moreover, it has places significant cognitive load on DT engineers, who manually interpret unstructured technical document to construct DT models and deploy compliant instances within DT platforms. The emergence of Large Language Models (LLMs), particularly Agentic AI, has motivated us to leverage these technologies for supporting engineering DT in collaboration with human. We intended to focus on the capabilities of Natural Language Processing (NLP) capabilities of LLM to transform and synthesise the unstructured technical documents into DT models. We devised an integrated architecture-centric approach that combines AI agents and human-in-the-loop (HITL) workflows with traditional DT platform capabilities to develop, deploy and operate DTs. This paper reports the foundation of our research that has conceptualise our vision of Agentic AI based platform for engineering DT, identification of requirements, and an architecture for Agentic AI based framework for engineering DT. We have present a Proof-of-Concept (PoC) implementation of the designed architecture using open-source components. Preliminary evaluation results show measurable reduction in modelling effort, while revealing the challenges in schema compliance and semantic consistency.

Index Terms—Digital Twin, Open Source, Artificial Intelligence, Digital Twin Modelling, Architecture, Digital Twin Engineering

I. INTRODUCTION

Digital twins (DTs) are virtual replicas of physical or digital systems that mirror their state and behaviour (e.g., systems, processes) through continuous synchronisation or predictive simulation. DTs have been widely adopted in different domains (e.g., farming, energy grid, and cybersecurity) to support decision-making processes [1]–[3].

Engineering of a DT usually involves designing, developing, deploying and operating a virtual replica of a physical/digital system. This process can be organised into three interconnected phases: Data acquisition, DT modelling and DT instantiation [4], [5]. The data acquisition phase focuses on identifying the relevant data sources (e.g., datasets, document, sensors) related to the virtualised entity, while obtaining the relevant general and operational data from those sources. The DT modelling phase focuses on the creation of *DT model*, which provides the architectural specification for the DT to be constructed. In particular, these models can specify (1) the

digitalised features and attributes that are mirrored from the physical counterpart, such as its physical weight, height or temperature, moisture readings that contribute to its states, and (2) the semantics and ontology that establishes the contextual and hierarchical relationship of the physical counterpart, such as what system it belongs to or what it measures [4], [5]. DT engineers often need to go through unstructured documents to interpret and extract all the needed knowledge to construct a DT models [5]–[7]. Finally, in the DT instantiation phase, engineers would interact with registry services employed in a DT platform, to create and register *DT instances* that conform to the defined DT model. Once instantiated, these DT instances can later be connected to data synchronisation, ingestion, preprocessing and visualisation services, which are outside the scope of the automation targeted in this work.

In addition to traditional software engineering and big data operations challenges, engineering a DT presents several unique challenges characterised by the need of extensive knowledge and skills and the significant cognitive load on engineers. For traditional DT frameworks, engineers must manually interpret technical documents to align sensor semantics with DT states [5], [8]. As the physical entity being virtualised grows in scale and complexity, such processes become increasingly time-consuming and labour-intensive. For example, suppose that we want to construct a DT of a cold storage facility for status monitoring and the estimation of the impact of IT/OT integration in the event of a cyber attack from the IT side. In this case, the necessary data to construct a DT could include humidity and temperature readings at various locations within the facility, which together can create a high enough fidelity to meet the requirements. A DT model in this context describes the data model of the physical state, which in turn drives the selection and transformation of data, as well as the alignment of their semantics. For instance, if a state ‘overheating’ need to be inferred from temperature readings above 28 Celsius at certain locations, corresponding sensors need to be identified and have their semantics aligned. If sensors used for these readings come from different manufacturers and use different measurement units, they also need to be adjusted.

Creating a DT model that drives all of these aspects requires extracting relevant information from technical documents of the related sensors or data sources, which may differ substantially in style, structure and complexity [9]–[11]. These types

of tasks require substantial amount of manual effort to locate specifications, identify components, features, attributes and their relationships from unstructured text, tables and scattered information. However, it has been demonstrated that the tasks related to transforming and synthesising unstructured technical documents can be effectively and efficiently performed using NLP capabilities of modern LLMs, which stimulated our interest in exploring the viability of using them for supporting DT engineering.

Hence, we decided to develop and implement an architectural framework to support DT engineering using Agentic AI to address these labour-intensive challenges and the cognitive load that characterises DT engineering. Our approach combines LLM-based AI agents and human-in-the-loop (HITL) workflows with traditional DT platform capabilities to develop, deploy and operate DTs. Our AI-Enabled architecture-centric DT engineering approach helps locate and retrieve the required knowledge [12], [13], summarise system context and hierarchical structure [5], process data tables [14], [15], and even instantiate a DT model by utilising given tools [16], [17]. Therefore, our research addresses a key research challenge: *devising and implementing a suitable architecture-centric framework for AI-Enabled DT engineering, which supports document processing, knowledge extraction, DT model creation and instantiation whilst integrating seamlessly with traditional DT platform capabilities.*

Our work contributes to the research efforts purport to leverage LLMs technologies for DTs with a clear focus on architectures of such systems. We conceptualised an AI-enabled framework for DT engineering, identified its requirements, and devised an architecture that is suitable to orchestrate an Agentic AI (i.e., consisting of multi-agents) workflows with HITL verification. Our approach enables seamless integration of AI capabilities into existing DT platform architectures, demonstrating how multi-agent systems and HITL workflows can be architected to work within DT platform ecosystems and enable Agentic AI DT engineering. We developed and evaluated a Proof-of-Concept (PoC) using architecture-centric approach implemented with Open Source technologies. The preliminary evaluation shows that our approach reduces the effort required for DT engineering compared with manual work; it also reveals several challenges in schema compliance and semantic representation consistency.

II. BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

DT engineering generally involves four consecutive tasks, which are data acquisition and processing, DT modelling and instantiation [4], [18]. At first, the data source of target physical entity will be identified, along with its general and operational data available. After the purpose and level of fidelity of a DT is determined, relevant data will be identified, while semantics and ontology of the target physical entity will be analysed. After that, DT model will be created with knowledge obtained from previous tasks, including the digitalised features and attributes that contribute to its states, as well as its contextual and hierarchical relationships. Finally, DT model

will be instantiated and deployed in the dedicated DT services, which can then be used for the desired application.

For traditional DT framework, these tasks are manually carried out [5], [8]. Lack or absence of appropriate suitable automation support to facilitate DT engineering processes, which make them challenging and error-prone. Because when a physical entity that is being virtualised grows in scale and complexity, such process becomes time-consuming and labour-intensive. As for each DT instance that needs to be created, these tasks are performed sequentially to acquire and analyse the necessary information, then develop the model in specific format like JSON and manually instantiate them [19].

Since many commonalities between DTs from different domains exist in terms of their software, logic and underlying support infrastructure, recreating these systems from scratch for every new use case is inefficient [20]. Several platforms and frameworks for creating and operating DTs are available.

Eclipse Ditto is an Open Source framework for creating, managing and interacting with DTs of physical entities [21]. It not only provides a way for modelling physical entities in the digital space, but also provides software and infrastructure support for accessing, updating and synchronising the state of connected entities in real time. As an Open Source instantiation of fully functioning DT framework, OpenTwins framework has been constructed on top of Eclipse Ditto [22]. It provides an open and containerised microservices stack, that fills functional gaps required for the operational DTs.

Our work specifically targets the reduction of cognitive and technical load placed on engineers during DT modelling and instantiation. Rather than requiring engineers to manually interpret technical documents, extract relevant information, and construct DT models and their instances, our approach automates these tasks using AI agents. Our Agentic AI approach complements existing DT platforms by enabling automated extraction and structuring of system knowledge into DT compliant representations. By focusing on automating the data acquisition, DT modelling and instantiation, our approach enhances platform usability and supports scalable DT engineering whilst preserving human oversight.

The adoption of LLM for automating and streamlining the generation of DT has also been explored. For example, ChatTwin demonstrates the feasibility of leveraging GPT-4 to transform textual descriptions into structured DT model/scene description files [19]. However, its primary focus lies in scene and configuration generation under Segment-and-Generate workflow on natural language input.

We have focused on broader architectural problem of integrating AI agents into end-to-end DT engineering workflow, which combines multiple AI agents with HITL verification to support the workflow from document processing and knowledge extraction to DT model creation and instantiation. Moreover, our work is constructed entirely from Open Source components. As we expect researchers and practitioners to inspect, reuse and replicate our setup, whilst tailoring to their own use cases, lowering barriers to further research and practice of AI-Enabled engineering of DT.

Fig. 1. DT engineering phases and required efforts divided by agent

III. REQUIREMENTS & DESIGN RATIONALE

A. From manual process to Agentic AI workflow

As DT engineering can be organised into three interconnected phases. Among these phases, engineers of traditional DT framework are required to perform a sequence of tasks as shown in Figure 1, which can be viewed as either intellectual, analytical cognitive tasks or practical, hands-on manual tasks.

Data Acquisition: Engineers need to identify the physical entities to be virtualised, as well the general and operational information available in their documents. General information includes static elements such as specification, configuration and topology. Operational information includes data produced during operation, such as data readings or computed results.

DT Modelling: Engineers need to determine a DT's purpose and required fidelity. They also need to identify the features and attributes to be digitalised, where attributes summarise the static general information and features summarise the dynamic operational information. Furthermore, engineers need to understand contextual or hierarchical relationship of the virtualised entity by analysing its semantics and ontology. Based on this information, a DT model can be created as an architectural specification that defines to show the digital twin is structured.

DT Instantiation: Engineers need to interact with registry services employed in a DT platform, to create and register DT instances that conform to the defined DT model. This requires invoking relevant APIs and adhering to the required schema and syntax to ensure DT instances are correctly structured and deployed. Once instantiated, these DT instances can later be connected to data synchronisation, ingestion, preprocessing

and visualisation services, which are outside the scope of the automation targeted in this work.

To reduce a DT engineer's workload, we introduced AI agents, that share the responsibility across different phases by generating the required knowledge and performing relevant tasks. Thus, whilst more than half of the required cognitive and manual tasks are taken away by agents, engineers only need to perform less intensive tasks such as identifying entities to be virtualised and their documents, defining DT purpose and fidelity, and verifying validity and consistency of agent outputs at each phase.

B. Requirements for Integration of DT Engineering Framework and Agentic AI Automation

To ensure the required tasks can be completed by the developed framework, there are requirements that need to be considered, as shown in Table I. DT engineering requirements define the capabilities necessary to represent and instantiate DTs within a DT platform and to enable interaction between framework and existing services, which are independent of the automation mechanism used to create them. *D1* allows framework to represent DT models in a structured semantic format that captures entities, attributes and relationships of the target system. *D2* and *D3* allow framework to create and deploy compliant DT instances by interacting with existing DT platform services and adhering to a platform's data schema and APIs. *D4* allows a created DT and its components to be recurrently adapted and reused, whilst letting engineer to modify or swap out components or services, to tailor the framework to fit their own needs or resources.

The requirements for automation with Agentic AI arise from the need to automate the DT engineering tasks using AI

agents while ensuring reliability, controllability and human oversight. *A1* and *A2* allow framework to extract relevant DT modelling information from unstructured technical documentation, summarise and transform these knowledge into structured representations suitable for DT modelling. *A3* allows framework to incorporate HITL verification to iteratively review, refine and approve agent generated outputs at each step of the workflow. Where as *A4* allows these interdependent tasks to be systematically decomposed, coordinated and executed by specialised AI agents, ensuring separation of concerns, controllable workflow sequencing and scalable automation of the DT engineering tasks. These requirements together motivate an architecture that integrates agent orchestration, HITL verification and DT platform services to support automated yet reliable DT engineering.

TABLE I
REQUIREMENTS FOR INTEGRATION OF DT ENGINEERING FRAMEWORK
AND AI-AGENT AUTOMATION

ID	DT Engineering Requirements
<i>D1</i>	DT Model Representation
<i>D2</i>	DT Model Instantiation
<i>D3</i>	DT Platform Integration
<i>D4</i>	Framework Modularity & Reusability
ID	AI-Agent Automation Requirements
<i>A1</i>	Information Extraction from Input
<i>A2</i>	Semantic Interpretation & Structuring
<i>A3</i>	HITL Verification & Iterative Refinement
<i>A4</i>	Multi-Agent Workflow Orchestration

IV. AN AI-ENABLED DT ENGINEERING FRAMEWORK: WORKFLOW, ARCHITECTURE & ITS COMPONENTS

A. The Workflow

Figure 2 shows the workflow of our AI-enabled (i.e., Agentic AI) approach, and how different requirements from Table I are satisfied. To satisfy *A1* and *A4*, the *Workflow Orchestrator* manages both human interaction and workflow automation. Its responsibilities include prompting, managing inter-agent inputs/outputs, as well as tracking workflow status and context. It processes input instructions and documents, reports progress of each step and uses human feedback to proceed or repeat steps.

To satisfy *A1* and *A2*, the *General & Operational Data Analyser* and *Semantics & Ontology Analyser* are introduced to manage the extraction of information, as well as summarisation and structuring of knowledge. *DT Creator* on the other hand, manages the interaction with services for DT modelling and instantiation, which satisfy *D1, D2* and *D3*. To be more specific, the *General & Operational Data Analyser* parses documents passed from the Workflow Orchestrator using the document reader tool. It extracts general and operational knowledge required for digitalising features and attributes, used as the first component of a DT model. On the other hand, the *Semantics & Ontology Analyser* then analyses the document using previously generated knowledge as context. From semantic and ontological knowledge, it derives context

and relationship to digitalised features and attributes. Building up structure and hierarchy as the second component of a DT model. Then, the *DT Creator* combines knowledge and outputs from the previous steps to define a DT model. In addition to external knowledge on the format and API syntax required by a DT service, it constructs a DT model and builds the necessary API calls for instantiation.

Between each step, HITL verification allows engineers to ensure the quality and validity of agent outputs. Engineers can request a rerun with corrections when outputs of a step is unsatisfactory. This iterative workflow enables continuous refinements and elaboration until we achieve the desired outcome, thus satisfies *A3*. To satisfy *D4*, the agentic module not only enables engineers to customise the given instructions and tools, but also to swap the LLM model used for any agent in the workflow. While tools can be created, modified and reused across agents.

B. The Architecture & its components

Figure 3 shows the general architecture and its components underpinning our framework for Agentic AI for DT engineering. There are three main parts in our framework’s architecture, the data sources, the agentic AI DT module, and the DT platform (DTP) layers where the module can be integrated.

1) *Data source*: Our framework considers two types of data sources as input. One is IoT data source and another is entity document. IoT data source is not our main focus, rather we just focus on the data read from a physical entity to be mirrored onto DT instance. The entity documents are composed of textual document and human instruction. This source is required for workflow orchestrator agent for initiating the subsequent workflow.

2) *Agentic DT module*: As the core component that supports the Agentic AI workflow, the agentic DT module is composed of two open-source frameworks, the *OpenTwins* and *Mastra*.

OpenTwins provides the “front-end” for managing a DT instance. It enables a way to define a DT with a unified model, and reuse any developed model or instance as a part of other model or instance. Thus, its adoption contributes to the requirements *D1, D2, D3*, and satisfy the *D4* mentioned in the Table I. To be more specific, Eclipse Ditto acts as the core service that provides this framework a defined structure to work on DT, whether that is the creation, management or other aspects. Eclipse Ditto in combination to Grafana and specialised plugin extension allow us to create a template/blueprint for the creation of DT instance, which is called “Type” in OpenTwins. By efficiently creating an instance from “Type” that is called “Thing”, we do not have to create each DT instance from scratch. In addition, as we can create an hierarchical relationship between DTs, we can use them to represent and model any hierarchical or compositional relationship between physical entities in the real-world. For instance, we can reuse a “Type” we defined to create a

Fig. 2. The workflow of AI-enabled DT engineering

“Thing”, and make that “Thing” as a parent or children of another “Thing” we created before.

Mastra provides a way to create Agentic AI support for workflow for automating DT engineering, covering from data acquisition to DT modelling and instantiation. By providing explicit definitions, we can create agents with clear responsibility boundaries by giving them role based instructions, workflows, as well as customised tools available and reusable for these agents. Moreover, textual based interaction facilitates the HITL verification for agent outputs, whilst modular agent and tool architecture enables independent extension, replacement and reuse of components without affecting the overall workflow. Thus, its adoption satisfy the requirements from *A1* to *A4*, and *D4* as mentioned in Table I.

DTP Layers indicates the places where Mastra and OpenTwins can be integrated into an existing DT platform without replacing its core services. Rather than restructuring the platform, we introduce them as additional service components. OpenTwins functions as the DT modelling and management service, whilst Mastra operates as an automated DT model construction and instantiation service. Integration occurs through defined platform interfaces, including API interaction, data storage (InfluxDB) and UI extensions. For example, helper functions can be implemented to query DT data stored in InfluxDB, whilst a streaming pipeline can periodically synchronise updates for dashboard visualisation. By positioning Mastra and OpenTwins as modular services within specific DTP layers, the architecture preserves traditional DT platform capabilities whilst augmenting them with Agentic AI based engineering support.

3) *Dynamic view of the DT creation run*: Figure 4 shows the workflow of our approach to engineer a DT. The workflow starts when an engineer provides the instruction and documents to the automated DT instantiation services. Upon

receiving the information, the workflow orchestrator agent calls the specific worker agent at each step for either analysing corresponding information or constructing the API call. By running these agents, knowledge regarding entity, modelling or instantiation will be stored and made available to both agents and engineer, who can decide to reject the outcome produced by a worker agent at any step; the orchestrator agent will call that agent again for redo with engineer’s additional instruction for correction. Once an engineer accepts the API call constructed by DT creator agent, orchestrator agent will provide the formatted API call as result.

V. EVALUATION & CASE STUDIES

We have evaluated the effectiveness and practicality of the proposed Agentic AI DT engineering framework using two aspects:

- Effort reduced to instantiate DT from its document
- Accuracy of the instantiated DT

A. Evaluation procedure

To measure the effort reduced by adopting the agentic workflow, we recorded the total time spent on manual DT instantiation and used it as the baseline. It was then compared with the runtime of the agentic workflow from the same input, to compute the percentage reduction in effort. Per-agent step time and HITL runtime were also extracted from execution logs, enabling calculation of the ratio between HITL effort and the residual manual effort.

To measure the accuracy of the DT instances generated by the agents, we compared the agent-generated API calls with manually created baseline API calls. In terms of completeness of features and attributes, correctness of semantic/ontological relationships, and schema compliance required by Ditto’s APIs. To measure completeness, it was quantified using

Fig. 3. Architecture of Agentic AI based approach to DT engineering

Feature Coverage Accuracy (FCA) and Attribute Coverage Accuracy (ACA). FCA is the fraction of baseline features correctly captured by the agent, whilst ACA is the fraction of baseline attributes captured.

B. Evaluation setup and input artefacts

The evaluation has been conducted using a case study that constructs DT of a room with information from different sensors. To facilitate the practical feasibility and reproducibility, we used an Open Source framework for whose details are summarised in Table II. Our Mastra framework developed and used for evaluation are available on zenodo [23]. Gemini-2.5-flash was selected for our agents due to its accessibility and optimisation for rapid inference, which supports robust function/tool calling, making it well-suited to multi-step, tool-augmented agentic workflows.

TABLE II
SOFTWARE AND FRAMEWORK USED FOR THIS PROJECT

Software/Framework	APP Version
OpenTwins	OpenTwins-0.5.17
Mastra	@mastra/core 0.13.2
LLM	gemini-2.5-flash
Flask	2.2.5
Airflow	3.0.0

The workflow takes three IAQ sensor manuals as input, each with distinct style, structure and complexity [9]–[11]. They provide specifications needed for DT modelling, including device attributes like connection available, power source, measurement ranges; measurable features like PM_{2.5}, CO₂, temperature, humidity; as well as hierarchical relationships among sensors and pollutants they measured. The expected outputs are complete and functioning API calls for instantiating DT instances in Ditto. Each capturing the correspond-

ing integrated sensor’s attributes and features, along with a structured model of its semantics and ontology that can be reviewed and modified in JSON style. In addition, a baseline of attributes (identity and sensing capabilities) and features (physical properties measured) was manually established for the three sensors to serve as the evaluation ground truth.

C. Evaluation results and analysis

As shown in Table III, the total time spent on both manual and agentic instantiation approaches varies across documents. In this case, total time recorded for Agentic AI approach accounts the time spent on both HITL workflow and manual syntax correction after the workflow, which will be explained later in this section.

TABLE III
TOTAL TIME SPENT ON EACH DOCUMENT FOR MANUAL AND AGENTIC AI APPROACH

Sensor	Manual	Agentic	% Reduction
eSol	11 min 05 s	10 min 04 s	9.1%
WH45	25 min 32 s	16 min 17 s	36.2%
Honeywell	26 min 42 s	18 min 24 s	31.1%

Results from the WH45 and Honeywell sensors indicate that the agentic workflow performs as expected, which substantially reduced the effort required to read, process and generate the knowledge needed for DT modelling. Instead of requiring 25 and 26 minutes respectively, the agentic AI workflow reduced the time spent on most steps to around 1 minute or less, achieving an overall time reduction of approximately 36.2% for WH45 and 31.1% for Honeywell. In contrast, the eSol document is considerably shorter and simpler in terms of its description, terminology and page count. Consequently, the time difference between the manual

Fig. 4. DT creation run from document to instantiation

and Agentic AI approaches is much smaller, with the agentic workflow offering only about a 9.1% reduction.

TABLE IV
ACCURACY METRICS ON API CALLS FOR EACH DOCUMENT

Sensor	FCA	ACA
eSol	100%	71.4%
WH45	100%	71.4%
Honeywell	100%	71.4%

By examining the raw outputs of the API calls, as well as calculating the Accuracy Metrics shown in Table IV, we gained insight into the accuracy of the generated DT instances. For FCA, as API calls produced for all three documents contain a complete set of features, matching and in some cases exceeding our baseline, they all achieved 100% in this metric. For ACA, API calls produced for all three documents were identified to have their temperature and humidity ranges appear inside feature properties, not attributes, and two of them have operating temperature and humidity recorded in attributes instead. Missing of two out of seven attributes have resulted 71.4% in this metric for all three documents. Despite the misplacement of fields, this result demonstrates that the agentic AI based workflow has the capability to extract sufficient knowledge about the virtualised entity.

However, the semantics and ontology reflected in these API calls are only partly correct. As misplacement, duplication of fields (key-value pairs) and the use of synonyms occurred frequently. For example, both “communication” and “connectivity” include a “frequency” subfield with the same value; “power consumption” and “power” has same value but listed

in different levels. More critically, its structural compliance with the schema appears problematic. Although all required fields are present, the overall structure still requires thorough manual correction, even when the correct schema is explicitly provided in the agent’s prompt. For example, key fields such as “policyId”, “attributes” and “features” appeared multiple times and nested in the wrong order, while some other fields in features should be actually listed in attributes. In JSON-style API calls, these fields should appear only once at their corresponding levels, but the agent recorded multiple of them in wrong order, necessitating the manual syntax correction. This requirement of manual syntax correction has created the residual manual effort before actual instantiation.

TABLE V
TIME SPENT ON EACH DOCUMENT FOR HITL WORKFLOW AND MANUAL SYNTAX CORRECTION

Sensor	HITL	Syntax	HITL/Syntax Ratio
eSol	5 min 11 s	4 min 53 s	1.06
WH45	7 min 34 s	8 min 43 s	0.87
Honeywell	8 min 03 s	10 min 21 s	0.78

To show how these manual corrections contributes to the total time cost of the agentic workflow, we have created the Table V. The time spent on the HITL workflow managed by Workflow Orchestrator agent were recorded separately in the HITL column, which includes the time spent on individual agentic steps; while the time spent on manual syntax correction accounts for the remainder of the total time, and recorded in Syntax column. For the WH45 and Honeywell documents, manual syntax correction required 13% and 22% more time

than HITL verification, indicating that schema misalignment contributes as a major source of the residual manual effort. In contrast, the eSol document shows comparable HITL and correction times due to its smaller content size and lower complexity.

Overall, these preliminary findings reveal a dual outcome: the agentic AI based workflow is highly beneficial for processing heterogeneous and complex documents, where simpler documents yield limited efficiency gains. But it concurrently struggles to enforce a consistent schema when generating semantics and ontology. This struggle results in significant issues like duplicated/redundant fields, inconsistent terminology, and structural errors in the final API calls.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presents an architecture-centric approach to engineering DT using Agentic AI workflow. The proposed workflow and architecture have been implemented using open source solutions, such as Mastra and OpenTwins. The PoC implementation demonstrates how LLM-based AI agents and HITL can support DT engineering for reducing manual effort and cognitive load required to transform unstructured document into instantiated DT models, while explicitly defining the architectural integration points and responsibilities of agent-based automation within a DT platform.

Preliminary evaluation shows reduction in document processing and modelling efforts. Whilst general and operational data are extracted effectively, there are limitations in schema compliance and the consistency of semantic and ontological structures. Our evaluation highlights both the potential and the current limitations of using Agentic AI for DT engineering workflow. The future research should focus on enhancing its robustness, scalability and correctness for larger and more complex DT applications. Whilst attribute and feature extraction is generally reliable, there are challenges in schema compliance, semantic consistency and ontology alignment, requiring residual manual correction. The workflow does not yet address conflicting or incomplete information across documents, nor does it analyse the contribution of individual agents or the impact of different LLM choices. Finally, the evaluation considers only one DT usage perspective, while different DT purposes (e.g., monitoring vs. simulation) may influence modelling requirements and workflow behaviour.

We plan to evaluate our approach across larger and more diverse domains by conducting comparative studies with alternative methods, and developing mechanisms for conflict resolution and automated consistency enforcement.

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